

CODA BASED APPROACH TO SURFICIAL AND TILL GEOCHEMISTRY

by

Charmee Kalubowila¹, Pertti Sarala¹, Patricia Puchhammer², Peter Filzmoser², Lucija Dujmovic³ and Solveig Pospiech³

¹*Oulu Mining School, P.O. Box 3000, FI-90014 University of Oulu, Finland*

E-mail: charmee.kalubowila@oulu.fi

²*Technical University of Vienna, Austria*

³*Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf e.V. (HZDR), Germany*

Compositional data (CoDa) are the data that can be summed up to a fixed constant (e.g., percentages, proportions) and these data contains the ratios between measured components that represent relative information between measurements (Filzmoser et al. 2018). Geochemical data is also considered as compositional data and targeting till, regional till and rock geochemical datasets of Finland are the three main datasets that are going to be considered in this abstract. The targeting till geochemical data set contains around 385 000 soil samples collected by the Geological Survey of Finland (GTK) along sample lines in certain areas between the years from 1971 to 1983. The point density of the samples lies between 6-12 samples per km². An emission quantometer method has been used to measure the concentration of 17 elements (Gustavsson et al. 1979). The other till geochemical data set is the regional till data which cover whole Finland and has been collected during 1983 to 1991. This data set contains the concentrations of 22-26 elements (depending on the map sheet) and the sampling density is one sample per 4 km² including the full data set of 82 062 samples (Salminen & Tarvainen 1995). The rock geochemical dataset contains the concentrations of different elements in Finnish bedrock for 6544 samples. The sampling has been done between 1990 and 1995 and the sampling density differs between one sample per 30-120 km² (Geological Survey of Finland 2007).

In this abstract, a subset of data from the Central Lapland area, Finland (Figure 1) has been considered. The selected subset of the regional till data generally has good data quality. However, for some elements it contains values below the lower detection limit, and some special symbols associated with specific data quality issues whereas rock geochemical dataset was associated with some values below the lower detection limit. Therefore, additional data cleaning is required. Compared to the previous data sets, the targeting till geochemical data set has serious data quality issues, typically connected to values related to detection limits, zeros and even negative analytical results, and values marked with special symbols. Therefore, extensive data cleaning was required.

Q-Q plots are used to evaluate the distribution of concentrations between different map sheets in the regional as well as in the targeting till data sets to analyse the mismatch between map sheets (Figure 2). The Q-Q plots vary quite strongly between map sheets M4, M5, M11, M12 (Figure 1) for the element Ni, as well as between targeting and regional till data sets despite compositional transformation. This might be either a result of levelling problems between map sheets or the distribution of the Ni concentration may change across the map sheets. Thus, it was decided not to combine the values from the map sheets in the analysis, but to analyse the map sheets (1:100 000 scale) separately, as the small areas contain enough sample points to carry out the analysis. However, the differences between the two data sets might be mainly due to different analytical techniques.

Figure 1. Study area in Finland (Central Lapland area) marked in grey color triangles (regional till data points), green color dots (targeting till data points) and M1, M4, M5, M11, M12 map sheets.

Figure 2. Q-Q plots of Ni: (a) original concentration in targeting till, (b) clr transformed concentration in targeting till, (c) original concentration in regional till, (d) clr transformed concentration in regional till, n (line till) = 16460, n (regional till) = 870.

PCA maps were generated for the selected area (M1) which contains two Ni-Cu-PGE deposits (Sakatti and Kevitsa - Figure 2), by considering all 3 data sets separately. The intention was to understand the link between underlying geology and geochemical analyses results. According to PCAs, the 3 data sets indicate three different relationships between Ni and Cu for the same area M1. The reason for having different correlation for Ni and Cu between targeting and regional till data sets is not clear, as the same till material has been used in two datasets except for the analysis method. However, the loadings for Cu are lower in both targeting and regional till data sets whereas it is higher in the weathered bedrock PCA, which could indicate some sort of deficiency in releasing Cu containing minerals to the till. In lithochemical data set, there are a few data points (23) that have been collected from weathered bedrock and the sampling points are sparse. This may cause a lack of correlation between Ni and Cu in the weathered bedrock PCA. Thus, it may show an entirely different correlation with Ni and Cu than in till. In all three plots Ti, V and Al positively correlate with each other.

Figure 3. PCAs of selected area M1 (a) targeting till (b) regional till (c) weathered bedrock.

Another approach in surficial geochemistry is to test how upper soil weak leach geochemical methods and biogeochemistry is working in tracing the critical metal sources in different soil types and landuse areas in Europe. The target areas locate in Czech Republic, Finland, Poland and Portugal. Aims are to test if the deposit is detectable at the surface, influence of the bedrock lithology, and the influence of surface cover on the geochemical signal on thick sediment cover such as a top of esker and typical till cover.

The first testing of surficial geochemical exploration methods was carried out in July 2022 at the Akanvaara test site (V-Cr-PGE layered intrusion) in Finland. The test includes both upper soil and plant sampling from 86 sampling stations which were chosen over the known layered intrusion at the boreal forest environment. For the soil analyses samples were collected from Ah, B and C horizons of the Podsol-type soil, and for the plant analyses different plant materials such as Common juniper twigs and needles, Labrador tea twigs, Norway spruce twigs and needles, Norway spruce bark as well as Pinecones were used.

Preliminary results show a significant response to many elements with known mineralized bedrock targets observed in the drill core data and exploratory data suggest that Ni behaves same manner with Co, Cd and less with Cu. As an example, Cu and Ni concentrations by the Ionic leach analytical methods in the upper soil samples is presented in Figure 4. Elemental distribution is also reflecting the lithological variations of the rock units in the bedrock. Based on the results, it is obvious that a) there is good or moderate correlation for several elements between the surface geochemical data and underlying bedrock, and b) soil analysis method using certain soil sampling procedure and selective extraction is an effective, environmentally friendly geochemical exploration technique in the glaciated terrains. However, later during this project statistical models based on the principles of compositional data analysis (CoDa-

principle) will be used to analyze these multi-variate and multi-parameter data sets for the major factors for element cycling between soil and plants.

Figure 4. Cu and Ni distribution in the Ionic leach results of Akanvaara area.

References

Filzmoser, P., Hron, K. & Templ, M. 2018. Applied compositional data analysis. Cham: Springer.

Geological Survey of Finland. 2007. Rock geochemical data of Finland. Available at: https://tupa.gtk.fi/paikkatieto/meta/rock_geochemical_data_of_finland.html (Accessed: 22.08.2023).

Gustavsson, N., Noras, P. & Tanskanen, H. 1979. Summary: Report on Geochemical mapping methods, Tech. rep., Geological Survey of Finland.

Salminen, R. & Tarvainen, T. 1995. Geochemical mapping and databases in Finland, *Journal of Geochemical Exploration* 55 (1-3), 321–327.